

Zooming in the work of EVORA's Work Package 7: terminology matters.

'It's JUST a matter of terminology...'. Surely you've heard this line when someone tries to reduce the importance that exact words have in the specific outcome of a discussion. But what if terminology does matter? Especially when it comes to the exact words describing research data that has to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) by the research community or by anyone interested really. Words have an impact. They affect the way we understand and think of information and concepts and, in the case of scientific research, they form our perception of what are the questions to be answered, for which objectives, and how do we design the scientific approach through which we will get our answers.

'Data Life Cycle Diagram' by [RDMkit](#) is licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#)

In the world of virology nomenclature keeps evolving; as research progresses and more information surfaces, virus species names, their parent taxa, and even entire lineage structures may change. Tracing the data linked to a specific virus, no matter what its name may be, can become nearly impossible in this changing landscape. Imagine wanting to buy some citrus fruit, say a lemon, but not knowing it is called 'lemon'. So you ask for an orange instead. Once you realise this is not what you were looking for, you go back and look at all the citrus fruit available at the stand, in order to find the lemon. How practical is this when you're looking for a virus sample or information related to it? This is where [EVORA](#) comes in, a project bringing together three expert research infrastructures in virology resource provision ([EVA](#)), high-containment facilities ([ERINHA](#)) and data management solutions ([ELIXIR](#)). One of EVORA's missions is smoothing out these terminology-related issues around virus nomenclature. Because it's not just terminology.

Here, Philippe Lieutaud, Chief Technical Officer of the European Virus Archive (EVA), and work package leader of WP7 in EVORA, discusses their ongoing work in the application of FAIR and Linked Open Data principles.

Speaking the same language

How can we discuss if we don't speak the same language? Creating a common vocabulary in virology is one of the aims of EVORA, in order to unify the descriptions of viral resources across databases so as to facilitate scientists in identifying resources and related information that is relevant to their research project.

'For this, we created the [EVORAO ontology](#), a set of terms describing the material and services offered by the research infrastructures in EVORA' starts Philippe. 'This vocabulary represents the terms and the relationships between them, is compliant with FAIR principles and based on community standards. Describing virology material and related services in a unified language facilitates metadata interoperability across research infrastructures, supports machine-readable exports, making it easier to integrate information and develop further tools' he adds.

The implementation of the EVORAO ontology marks a significant step forward for the semantic alignment of virology data and enables users and stakeholders, external to EVORA, to structure their catalogues for full interoperability with EVORA's ecosystem.

Classification matters

Taking a step further, EVORA worked on improving how ICTV taxonomy information can be accessed and followed-up. This contribution is bound to have high impact for the virology scientific community and for public health, as the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV) database gathers the official taxonomic names that enable virus classification into families and genera and is the globally accepted standard for virus classification. Nevertheless, these names may change over time with the input of new research data, making it tricky to track a virus and its synonyms across historical releases. As a result, scientists often have to go through laborious manual searches to retrieve taxonomic information on a given virus, trace the history of changes in the virus classification or find synonym identifiers for the same virus.

'Here the objective was to make scientists' lives easy by improving how virus taxonomic names can be found in the ICTV database', explains Philippe. For this, EVORA worked, in collaboration with the ICTV, on the creation of an application programming interface (API) by transforming the ICTV data into an ontology that can be queried through the [Ontology Lookup Service \(OLS\) API](#) of the [EMBL-EBI](#) (EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute). This interface allows scientists and data managers to find current virus names, historical labels and relationships, without manual detective work.

'It improves the accuracy and reproducibility of this data, by making the "what changed, when, and how" transparent and searchable by computer programmes. As a result, databases worldwide will be able to keep references up to date with latest releases of the official virus taxonomy' Philippe adds. Through this work EVORA contributes directly to the virology community, by rendering virology taxonomy information more easy to access and trace, and more broadly to the ability of scientists and public health stakeholders to rapidly respond in a pandemic crisis, therefore having a positive impact on public health.

Let's workshop this

Beyond the development of tools that facilitate virology data management, EVORA has engaged with the virology research community through a first online workshop titled "Unlock the power of your research data for global impact". In this event, EVORA partners shared insights into current research data management practices, decision-making structures and institutional challenges, and attracted the participation of the broader virology research community, confirming the relevance of the initiative. As a follow up, a [dedicated virology domain](#) was developed on RDMkit that includes references and descriptions of openly accessible resources, such as the EVORAO ontology, designed to help virology research data management.

'This new RDMKit domain addresses challenges in data heterogeneity, sensitivity, ethical considerations, and data sharing protocols, which can make a real difference in improving rapid response during pandemic' explains Philippe.

The next research data management workshop is coming up soon and is on [Viral Genome Assembly Submission to the European Nucleotide Archive](#) (ENA). The aim of this workshop is to demonstrate the new tool developed by EVORA for easy and streamlined genomic assembly submission to the European Nucleotide Archive. The workshop will also gather the attendees' feedback in order to contribute to the further development of this open-source tool.

Easy access

The future plans of EVORA WP7 include the design and implementation of a web application to serve as a central access point to virology resources and services provided by EVORA partners.

Follow-up activities include a 'content marathon' in early 2026 to refine the content of the RDMkit virology domain, and a final workshop in late 2026 focused on the sustainability of the developed material. These efforts aim to integrate the developed guidelines and tools within [ELIXIR](#), supporting long-term improvements in data management practices across the virology research landscape, beyond the EVORA project.

*Philippe contributes to European virology projects such as [ISIDORE](#) and EVORA. He has a background in full-stack development and bioinformatics, and his work focuses on IT infrastructures, data interoperability, and the application of FAIR and Linked Open Data principles.

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